

Online Education System During Covid-19: Challenges and Opportunities

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Abstract:

Online education is a method of teaching whether students can study online from stay home with the use of the internet, electronic devices like computers, laptops, smartphones and tablets etc. In this process, teachers and students can connect with each other from any corner of the world with the use of the internet. During Covid-19, many countries around the world including India have also closed their schools in order to get rid of the Covid-19 coronavirus epidemic, which has caused disruption in the education of children around the world. Corona has affected every aspect of human life. The all over world education sector is also affected. At the current time education system is moving towards e-education, Online education is encouraged in many countries including India. Since all children and students have access to the Internet today, it has also become a popular medium of education.

Keywords: *E-education, teleconferencing, virtual meetings, e-conferencing, MOOCs*

Introduction:

Online education is a method of teaching-learning through which students can study online from home from the Internet using their electronic devices like computers, laptops, smartphones and tablets etc. By using this medium teachers and students can connect with each other from any corner of the world with the use of the internet. During Covid-19, many countries around the world including India have also closed schools in order to get rid of the Covid-19 coronavirus epidemic, which has caused disruption in the education of children & students around the world. Schools & Colleges are opened and closed also, but online education was also made available to the children & students to continue their education, while many students were deprived of getting online education due to lack of resources. But, no doubt, students with weak economic conditions have been the most affected by the lockdown measures. Covid-19 has shown its impact in the field of education in many ways. All schools, colleges, coaching,

universities etc. were closed during the Corona period because the safety of students' lives was more important than their education. For this reason, more emphasis on online studies from home. Various measures have been taken by schools, colleges, coaching, universities, etc. to provide online education to students. Efforts have been made by these institutions to provide online education using various online platforms such as YouTube videos, mobile apps, online websites, webinars, video conferencing apps, etc. Various types of online learning courses or online learning apps were launched by these institutions. In this way, a new way of imparting education came in front of the people. Corona has affected every aspect of human life. The all over world education sector is also affected. During this pandemic, the study system was continued through the online system. And today Education is rapidly moving towards e-education. E-education refers to the education obtained in one's own place with the help of the internet and other communication tools. There are various forms of e-learning, which include web-based learning, mobile-based learning or computer-based learning and virtual classrooms etc. In the e-learning system, the study material is made available to the students with the help of many online tools”.

Review of literature:

Recently, several authors have researched to find solutions to problems in online teaching-learning during COVID-19, but most of the studies have addressed students' problems. In their study (**Gretz & Looney, 2020**) explored the desire of faculty teachers to teach online and their resistance to this change in Los Angeles, where teachers explicitly stated that they lacked the skills to teach online. **Arora and Srinivasan (2020)** identified the challenges of online learning as lack of network, training, awareness and interest, low attendance, lack of personal desire and lack of interaction. **Kaup et al. (2020)** noted the challenges related to technology, training and student engagement in continuing academics during the COVID-19 pandemic. There is not enough infrastructure like teachers' laptops, internet and microphones. Along with this many teachers face connectivity issues, system failure, bandwidth issues etc while conducting online sessions, and due to a lack of technical support, they are unable to solve the problems of teaching-learning (**Sharma, 2020**). Teachers also found it difficult to manage students in distance learning. **Jena, K. Pravat (2020)**, found in his study that Covid 19 has greatly affected the education sector in the Indian economy. Along with the challenges, it has also developed various opportunities. The government of India, private education institutions and various stakeholders of education have explored the potential of open and distance

education by adopting various digital technologies to promote education to tide over the current challenging crisis of COVID-19.

The objective of the study: The objectives of the study are as follows

- Through the present research paper, we will try to study the various online platforms which adopted by educational institutions to continue the teaching-learning process during the pandemic Covid-19.
- We will try to find out the measures taken by the Government of India to advance the online learning process during Covid-19.
- We will try to find out about the challenges, problems and solutions of the online teaching learning system.

Methodology:

In this present paper, necessary information and data are based on secondary data. For the study, information has been compiled from various reports and articles published by national and international journals. Few information has been taken from many websites and research papers. Along with this, different types of newspapers and magazines have also been made the basis of the study.

The platform of Online education:

Swayam: The objective of the SWAYAM education portal is to provide a learning platform to all, including the most disadvantaged in the economy. SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) is a program of Govt. of India. It hosts and provides all the courses taught in classrooms from Class 9th to post-graduation. In the SWAYAM platform learning process is being 4 types.

- 1- Video lecture
- 2- Specially prepared reading material that can be downloaded/printed
- 3- Self-assessment tests through tests and quizzes and
- 4- An online discussion forum for clearing doubts.

Diksha: DIKSHA is a medium of online education platform which stands for Digital Infrastructure for Knowledge Sharing and enhancing. It is currently used by teachers and students across the nation to provide school education through distance mode learning. Amidst the disruption of schooling education due to COVID-19, DIKSHA makes it maximum possible for all states and Union Territories to enable learning and education at home through innovative state programs. DIKSHA have been springing online technology for the benefit of teachers and

learners across India. This is a big effort of the NCERT, Government of India. DIKSHA can be accessed at diksha.gov.in by learners and teachers across the country. It currently supports various courses of NCERT, CBSE and SCERTs across India.

E-Shodh Sindhu: It will continue to provide current as well as archival access to more than 10,000 peer-reviewed journals and a number of bibliographic, citation and factual databases to its member institutions. E-ShodhSindhu can be accessed at ess.inflibnet.ac.in. Consortium for Higher Education e-Resources Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India has collaborated with 3 leading consortiums of India – UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, N-List and INDEST – AICTE Consortium for this e-Shodh Sindhu The consortium has been created as a higher education e-resource. Through this portal, more than 15 thousand latest and archival journals can be read through online e-learning on your computer, laptop or smartphone. These journals are core and peer-reviewed, containing multiple types of bibliographic, citation and factual databases. The best part is that e-Shodh Sindhu's database covers most of the subjects taught in various colleges, universities and CFTIs in the country. In these journals, most of the publishers along with the country's renowned universities and technical institutions are also involved in e-Shodh. Indus contributes to the consortium. The College Part-N-List of e-Shodh Sindhu Consortium has more than 65 hundred journals and more than 31,35,000 e-books which are useful for more than 3 thousand colleges. This online learning e-resource provides e-books and e-journals on a subscription basis to all educational institutions. E-Shodh Sindhu Consortium provides vital information to society and the country by bridging the digital gap.

E-PG Pathshala: E-Pathshala is an initiative taken by MHRD under its National Mission on Education in the country through ICT, which is being conducted by UGC. The platform, epgp.inflibnet.ac.in provides interactive e-content in 70 subjects in all disciplines of Social Sciences, Arts, Fine Arts and Humanities, and Natural and Mathematical Sciences.

Swayam Prabha: There are 34 DTH channels working under Swayam Prabha. They are broadcasting very high-quality educational programs 24X7. The course material under this is provided by NPTEL, IITs, UGC, CEC, IGNOU, NCERT and NIOS. The website is swayamprabha.gov.in.

NPTEL: The National Program on Technology Enhanced Education was started in 2003 by the Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore along with IIT Bombay, IIT Delhi, IIT Kanpur, IIT

Kharagpur, IIT Madras, IIT Guwahati, IIT Roorkee. NPTEL platform, nptel.ac.in offers open online courses around Engineering and Core Science subjects.

Result & Discussion:

Impact of Covid-19 on Education

During Covid-19, It has caused many negative impacts on education, but our educational institutions have accepted the challenge and made every effort to provide relentless support services to the students during this dreadful pandemic. COVID-19 has promoted digital technologies for educational work. Both teachers and students have adopted this technique. The use of Learning Management systems by educational institutions became a big demand. During this time the students were not able to collect the hard copy of the study material and hence most of the students used the soft copy material for reference. This pandemic has led us to use to huge teleconferencing, virtual meetings, webinars and e-conferencing etc. Learning materials were easily shared among students, and many questions were resolved by e-mail, phone calls, and using various social media such as WhatsApp and Facebook. This arrangement is providing opportunities to interact with teachers and students from all over the world. The education sector has suffered more due to the outbreak of Covid-19. Due to this pandemic, classes were kept suspended for a long time and examinations were postponed also. There was a gap in the admission process. Most of the recruitment stopped due to it. The unemployment rate increased exponentially. In such a situation, it was seen fighting for food by the people. Most of the teachers/students were not used to online virtual education. Most of the teachers were conducting lectures only on video platforms in the zoom, google meet etc which did not prove to be very useful.

Table- 1, Covid-19 and Education sector

Total students affected from COVID – 19 in India (Million)	
Sector	Affected
Pre-Primary	10 (3%)
Primary	143 (45%)
Secondary	133 (41%)
Tertiary	34 (11%)
Total	320

Source: UNESCO

Figure-1

230 million students in India were affected by Covid 19 which is given in table -1. There was the biggest impact seen on the tertiary sector ie senior secondary and higher education. The primary sector was more affected during Covid- 19 due to the unavailability of resources such as mobile, connectivity and unknowing about to social media. The higher education sector was also affected, but due to the technical knowledge of the students, there was some continuity of teaching-learning in this area. According to the Economic Survey 2020-21, India will have the largest youth population in the world by the next decade. Therefore, in order to prepare the future of the country, it is necessary to develop the capacity to provide high-quality education to these youth (New Education Policy 2020). As per UDISE 2018-19, there has been an unprecedented change in the physical infrastructure of 9.72 lakh government primary schools. Of these, 90.2 per cent of schools have toilets for girls and 93.7 per cent of schools have toilets for boys. 95.9% of the schools have drinking water facilities. Water for drinking, toilet and hand washing is available in 82.1 per cent of the schools. A medical check-up facility is available in 84.2 per cent of the schools. Computers are available in 20.7 per cent of schools and electricity connections in 67.4 per cent and ramp facilities are available in 74.2 per cent of schools along with other facilities.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the government has taken several positive initiatives to provide education to children and students. An important initiative in this direction is the

launch of PM-eVidya. This provides a multi-dimensional and level playing field for digital/online/on-air education for students and teachers. About 92 online courses have been started under Swayam Moocs (MOOCS) affiliated with the National Institute of Open Schooling (NIOS) and 1.5 crore students have enrolled themselves. To eliminate the impact of Covid-19, Rs 818.17 crore has been allocated to the States/UTs for providing online education through a digital medium. 267.86 crore has been released for providing online teacher training to teachers under the Samagra Shiksha Yojana. Pragma on Digital Education (PRAGYATA) guidelines have been prepared to provide online education at home to students due to the closure of schools due to the COVID pandemic. Manodarpan initiative has been started for psychological help in the self-reliant India campaign.

Conclusion: Many educational institutions have resorted to various platforms like Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Skype, WhatsApp, E-mail etc. to provide online live and recorded classes to the students. All these platforms are facilitating online teaching-learning between students and teachers. This period is important for the education sector because competitive examinations along with entrance work, board examinations, entrance examinations in universities, etc. are mainly conducted between March-June. Millions of children were literally denied education during the pandemic. Certainly, the right to education should be strengthened by rebuilding a better and more just & strong education system. Its purpose should not only be to restore the situation before the pandemic, but also to remove the shortcomings of the system, due to which the doors of schools and colleges have not been open for children and students for a long time. The education sector is still trying to grapple with disruption. It will definitely improve.

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